

PREVALENCE, CONTRIBUTING FACTORS, AND PERCEIVED STRESS ASSOCIATED WITH HAIR LOSS AMONG STUDENTS AND FACULTY MEMBERS IN A PRIVATE PHARMACY COLLEGE IN TELANGANA, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Background: The problem of HL is multifaceted, that affects individuals worldwide and is associated with both physiological and psychological influences. Several reasons, including stress, nutritional imbalances, hormonal fluctuations, hair grooming practices, and the application of hair care items can trigger it. This research intends to evaluate the incidence of HL, its contributing factors, and the associated stress levels perceived by students and faculty at a private pharmacy college located in Cheeryal, Telangana, India. **Aim:** To assess the prevalence of hair loss, its associated factors, and perceived stress among students and faculty members of a private pharmacy college in Telangana, India. **Methods:** A cross-sectional questionnaire-based study was conducted among pharmacy students and faculty members from July 2024 to January 2025. A pre-validated questionnaire was used which

included hair loss awareness questions, Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-4), Alopecia Areata Symptom Impact Scale (AASIS), and Modified Hairdex Questionnaire. Data were analysed using SPSS software. Chi-square tests and Spearman's correlation were used to determine associations between variables. Participants were selected through convenience sampling from a private pharmacy college. Informed consent was granted before distribution, and was carried out in a classroom setting. **Results:**

A total of 302 completed questionnaires were analysed from 305 distributed surveys (response rate: 99%). Most participants were aged 18–20 years (62%) and were female (72%). Approximately 40% of participants reported mild hair loss, while 19% reported significant hair loss. Moderate stress levels were observed among a majority of participants. Hair loss was significantly associated with academic stress, family history, and lifestyle factors ($p < 0.05$). Correlation analysis demonstrated relationships between psychological distress and hair loss-related factors. **Conclusion:** Significant factors involved are academic stress, anxiety, and distress related to self-perceived HL. The results emphasize the importance of focused mental health strategies to alleviate stress and enhance overall well-being, which could also aid in addressing HL issues.

KEYWORDS: Prevalence, Causes, Perceived Stress, Hair Loss, Pharmacy Students, Faculty.

INTRODUCTION

Hair loss (HL), also known as alopecia, is a common dermatological condition affecting individuals worldwide. It may occur due to multiple factors such as stress, nutritional deficiencies, hormonal imbalances, use of hair care products, and certain styling practices.^[1] Although hair loss is widely prevalent, it is often associated with significant psychosocial distress.^[2] Identifying the causes of hair loss is therefore important, as it can greatly influence an individual's self-esteem, emotional well-being, and overall quality of life.^[3]

Hair plays an important role in shaping personal identity and self-image. Sociological aspects such as hair density and appearance contribute significantly to an individual's self-confidence and perceived attractiveness.^[4] Scalp hair is commonly associated with youthfulness, gender identity, social status, and vitality.^[5] However, individuals experiencing daily hair shedding frequently encounter emotional discomfort and dissatisfaction with their appearance, often described as experiencing a "bad hair day."^[6] The loss of hair may also lead to psychological distress, social pressure, and emotional challenges, which can further exacerbate stress levels.^[7]

Globally, nearly half of the adult population experiences noticeable hair loss at some point in their lifetime.^[8] In Asia, the prevalence of hair loss is estimated to affect approximately 30–40% of adults, while in India the prevalence is reported to be even higher, affecting nearly 50–60% of individuals.^[9] Genetic factors play a crucial role in many types of alopecia, particularly androgenetic alopecia, although environmental factors such as stress, pollution,

and lifestyle changes have contributed to a growing incidence of hair loss among younger populations.^[10,11] Studies conducted in Telangana have reported hair loss prevalence ranging between 45% and 55%, largely influenced by modern lifestyle habits and environmental conditions.^[12]

Hair loss, particularly when it occurs at an early age, may have a profound psychological impact. Individuals affected by hair loss may experience reduced self-esteem, impaired body image, and emotional distress. The psychological burden may be greater among women, for whom hair is often associated with femininity, attractiveness, and social identity. Early onset hair loss can therefore significantly influence self-perception, academic performance, and social interactions.

Despite the increasing prevalence of hair loss and its psychological implications, limited research has explored the relationship between hair loss and perceived stress among students and faculty members in academic institutions. Therefore, the present study aimed to assess the prevalence of hair loss and the associated perceived stress among students and faculty members in a private pharmacy college, as well as to identify the contributing factors and psychological impacts related to hair loss.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

A cross-sectional observational study was conducted to assess the prevalence of hair loss and the associated perceived stress among pharmacy students and faculty members.

Study Setting and Duration

The study was carried out among students and faculty members of Geethanjali College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, India, between July 2024 and January 2025.

Study Population

The study population consisted of B.Pharm, M.Pharm, and Pharm.D students (Year 1–Year 6), as well as teaching and non-teaching staff of the institution.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

- B.Pharm, M.Pharm, and Pharm.D students (Year 1–Year 6)
- Teaching and non-teaching staff of the institution

- Participants willing to provide informed consent and participate in the study

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals unwilling to participate or provide informed consent
- Participants not belonging to Geethanjali College of Pharmacy
- Incomplete questionnaire responses

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

Participants were recruited using a snowball sampling method. Sample size was calculated using the Raosoft online sample size calculator with a 95% confidence interval, 5% margin of error, and 50% response distribution, resulting in a required sample size of 269 participants.

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected using a pre-validated structured questionnaire distributed to participants in a classroom setting after explaining the purpose of the study. Written informed consent was obtained prior to participation. Participants completed the questionnaires within approximately 20 minutes, and the completed responses were collected for analysis.

Development and Validation of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire was adopted and adapted from previously published studies. It consisted of multiple sections assessing sociodemographic characteristics, awareness of hair loss, psychological stress, and quality of life.

Content and construct validity were established through expert review by five academicians from the departments of Pharmacy Practice and Pharmacology. Face validation was conducted through a pilot study involving 19 participants, who provided feedback on clarity and comprehension of the questionnaire items. Necessary modifications were made based on their suggestions.

Reliability of the questionnaire was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which demonstrated excellent internal consistency for the study instruments.

Study Measures

Sociodemographic Characteristics

Participants provided information regarding age, gender, religion, education, marital status, dietary habits, family history of hair loss, hair styling practices, and location.

Awareness of Hair Loss

Awareness regarding hair loss was assessed using 15 questionnaire items addressing causes, preventive measures, and hair care practices.^[13] The awareness score ranged from 0–60, categorized as:

- Poor (0–30)
- Average (31–45)
- Good (46–60)

Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10)

Perceived stress was assessed using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), which evaluates individuals' stress levels over the previous month.^[14] Responses were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (“never”) to 4 (“very often”). The total score ranged from 0–40, categorized as:

- Low stress (0–13)
- Moderate stress (14–26)
- High stress (27–40)

Psychological Distress (PHQ-4)

Psychological distress was measured using the Patient Health Questionnaire-4 (PHQ-4) developed by Kroenke et al.^[15] This tool assesses symptoms of anxiety and depression using a 4-point Likert scale (0–3). Total scores range from 0–12, categorized as:

- None (0–2)
- Mild (3–5)
- Moderate (6–8)
- Severe (9–12)

Alopecia Areata Symptom Impact Scale (AASIS)

The Alopecia Areata Symptom Impact Scale (AASIS) was used to evaluate the impact of hair loss on quality of life.^[16] The scale assesses symptoms, emotional effects, and physical impact related to alopecia.

Modified Hairdex Questionnaire

Quality of life related to hair loss was assessed using the Modified Hairdex Questionnaire, which evaluates domains including symptoms, functioning, emotions, self-confidence, and

stigmatization.^[17] Scores range from 0–100, with higher scores indicating greater impairment in quality of life.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Normality of the data distribution was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. Since the data were not normally distributed, non-parametric statistical tests were applied.

Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or median with interquartile range (IQR) where appropriate.

Correlation analysis using Spearman's correlation coefficient was performed to evaluate relationships between study variables. A two-sided p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Geethanjali College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before participation, and confidentiality of participant information was maintained throughout the study.

RESULTS

Study Population Characteristics

A total of 302 participants were included in the study, comprising 278 students (92%), 19 teaching staff (6%), and 5 non-teaching staff (2%). The majority of the participants were aged 18–20 years (186, 62%), followed by those aged 21–23 years (75, 25%), while smaller proportions belonged to the 24–26 years (7, 2%) and >26 years (34, 11%) age groups.

Regarding religion, most participants were Hindu (251, 83%), followed by Muslims (25, 8%) and Christians (26, 8%). In terms of educational background among students, B.Pharm students constituted the largest group (156, 52%), followed by Pharm.D students (116, 38%), while M.Pharm (3, 1%) and Pharm.D Post Baccalaureate (3, 1%) represented smaller proportions.

With respect to the year of study, the majority of participants were in the first year (101, 33%), followed by the fourth year (64, 21%), second year (48, 16%), third year (41, 14%), sixth year (14, 5%), and fifth year (11, 4%). Most participants were single (265, 88%), while 26 participants (9%) were married and 11 participants (4%) reported being in a relationship.

Dietary patterns indicated that the majority of participants followed a mixed diet (222, 73%), followed by non-vegetarian diet (42, 14%), vegetarian diet (37, 12%), and eggetarian diet (1, <1%).

Regarding the duration of hair loss, 138 participants (46%) reported experiencing hair loss for less than one year, while 129 participants (43%) reported hair loss for 1–5 years, and 35 participants (12%) reported hair loss for more than five years. Detailed sociodemographic characteristics of the participants are presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics.

Variables	N (%)
Age in years (N=302)	
18-20 years	186 (62)
21-23 years	75 (25)
24-26 years	7 (2)
>26 years	34 (11)
Religion	
Hindu	251 (83)
Muslim	25 (8)
Christian	26 (8)
Category	
Student	278 (92)
Teaching staff	19 (6)
Non-Teaching staff	5 (2)
Education Staff	
Primary	1 (0)
Secondary	1 (0)
UG	16 (5)
PG	4 (1)
Phd	2 (1)
Education Student	
B Pharm	156 (52)
M Pharm	3 (1)
Pharm D	116 (38)
PB	3 (1)
Year of Study	
1st year	101 (33)
2nd year	48 (16)

3rd year	41 (14)
4th year	64 (21)
5th year	11 (4)
6th year	14 (5)
Marital Status	
Single	265 (88)
Married	26 (9)
In relationship	11 (4)
Diet	
Veg	37 (12)
Nonveg	42 (14)
Mixed diet	222 (73)
Eggetarian	1 (0)

Response towards family history of hair loss

Figure 1 shows that hearing loss was most commonly reported in fathers (43.04%), followed by mothers (24.68%) and male siblings (13.92%). Lower percentages in other relatives suggest a possible genetic pattern, with paternal history being the most prominent.

Figure 1: Family History of HL.

Response towards water used for hair loss

Figure 2 shows that hard water is the most commonly used for hair washing (40.19%), followed by lukewarm water (25.32%) and soft water (13.92%). Hot and cold water are used less frequently. The high use of hard water may suggest a possible contributing factor to hearing loss (HL).

Figure 2: Water used for Hair wash.

Response towards hair styling practices

Figure 3 shows that shampoo use is the most common hair practice (61.96%), followed by hair dyeing (15.26%) and heat styling tools (10.48%). Conditioners (9.79%) and serums (2.51%) are used less frequently. Overall, basic cleansing and aesthetic changes dominate, while heat styling and specialized treatments play a smaller role.

Figure 3: Hair styling practices.

Response towards hair care

This pie chart (Figure 4) "Hair Care," demonstrates that home care is the dominant approach, with 86% of participants indicating they primarily care for their hair at home. Salon visits account for 12% of responses, while a very small fraction (2%) consult a therapist or dermatologist for hair care. Parlour visits are negligible. This chart emphasizes the strong preference for home-based hair care routines compared to professional treatments.

Figure 4: Hair care.

Hair Loss Awareness

Participants’ awareness regarding hair loss and its contributing factors was assessed using a structured questionnaire. A considerable proportion of participants reported experiencing hair loss, with 40% reporting mild hair loss and 19% reporting significant hair loss. The majority of participants (63%) believed that stress is associated with hair loss. Awareness regarding medication-induced hair loss was high, with 75% identifying anti-cancer drugs as a potential cause. Similarly, 66% of participants identified iron deficiency as a contributing factor, while 62% reported increased protein intake as a preventive measure. Despite this awareness, a large proportion of participants (61%) had never used any treatment for hair loss, and 34% were uncertain about the effectiveness of available treatments. Awareness regarding hair transplantation was limited, with 28% of participants unaware of the procedure and 34% expressing uncertainty about its effectiveness.

Overall, the findings indicate moderate awareness levels regarding hair loss causes and management among the study population. Detailed responses are presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Responses towards Hair Loss Awareness.

No.	Variable	Frequency	Percent	P value
1.	Are you having any hair related problem leading to hair loss?			
	No	111	37	
	Not noticed any hair loss	12	4	
	Yes, but only slightly	121	40	<.001*
	Yes, Significantly	58	19	
2.	When did you first notice your hair loss?			
	Less than 6 months	62	20	
	6 months to one year	78	26	.293

	1 to 2 years	77	25	
	More than 2 years	85	28	
3.	How often should you evaluate the condition of your hair and scalp for signs of hair loss?			
	Never	56	18	
	Regularly (every monthly)	144	48	<.001*
	Occasionally (every 3 months)	81	27	
	Rarely (once in 6-12 months)	21	7	
4.	Have you ever used any treatment for hair loss?			
	No and not considering	184	61	
	No but considering	76	25	<.001*
	Yes currently using	25	8	
	Yes, but stopped	17	6	
5.	How effective do you think are the treatments for hair loss?			
	Not effective at all	56	18	
	Not very effective	103	34	<.001*
	Somewhat effective	125	41	
	Very effective	18	6	
6.	Do you believe that stress can cause hair loss?			
	No hair loss not linked to stress	17	6	
	not sure, no clear pattern	45	16	
	Low, but hair loss continues	49	16	<.001*
	Yes, recent stress and more hair shedding	191	63	
7.	Which one of the following hormonal imbalances can potentially cause hair loss?			
	Testosterone	101	33	
	Vasopressin	37	12	<.001*
	Progesterone	92	30	
	Melatonin	72	24	
8.	Which of medication causes hair loss?			
	Anti-Cancer drugs	226	75	
	Analgesics	37	12	<.001*
	Antidiabetic drugs	20	7	
	Antacids	19	6	
9.	Which Nutrition deficiency causes hair loss?			
	Iron deficiency	199	66	
	Vitamin K deficiency	66	22	<.001*
	Calcium deficiency	18	6	
	Potassium deficiency	19	6	
10.	Which of the following conditions/actions are prone to cause hair loss?			
	Dry Scalp	77	25	
	Split ends	51	17	<.001*
	Using a wide-tooth comb	9	3	
	Dandruff	165	55	
11.	Which dietary considerations are often suggested to stop hair loss?			
	Increase Salt intake	24	8	
	Increase sugar intake	28	9	<.001*
	Increase fiber intake	63	21	

	Increase protein intake	187	62	
12.	Which type of hair care product is generally considered beneficial for preventing hair loss?			
	Shampoo with harsh chemicals	46	15	<.001*
	Conditioner	60	20	
	Hair serums with minoxidil or biotin	185	61	
	Hair gel with high Alcohol content	11	4	
13.	How often do you evaluate the condition of your hair and scalp for signs of hair loss?			
	Never	53	17	<.001*
	Regularly (monthly)	162	54	
	Occasionally (every 6 months)	58	19	
	Rarely (once a year)	29	10	
14.	Which of the following actions do you take when you notice signs of hair loss?			
	Avoid discussing the issue with anyone	31	10	<.001*
	Start a new hair care routine with random products	118	39	
	Ignore the issue and hope it resolves on its own	88	29	
	Consult a healthcare professional or Dermatologist	65	21	
15.	Do you think hair transplantation is the last option for hair loss?			
	Not aware of hair transplantation	85	28	<.001*
	Negative (I have concerns about the risks or costs)	69	23	
	Neutral (I'm unsure about its effectiveness.)	104	34	
	Positive (It can be beneficial for many people.)	44	15	
*Chi square test; p<0.5 is statistically significant.				

Respond towards perceived stress scale (PSS-10)

Perceived stress among participants was assessed using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10). The majority of participants reported moderate levels of stress, with 33% experiencing stress “sometimes.” A notable proportion of participants reported difficulties in managing daily responsibilities, with 35% indicating inability to cope with tasks and 32% reporting feelings of anger due to uncontrollable situations.

Overall, the findings suggest that a significant proportion of participants experienced moderate perceived stress. Detailed results are presented in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Response towards the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10; N = 302) Questionnaire.

No.	Variables	NN (%)	AN N (%)	ST N (%)	FO N (%)	VO N (%)	P Values
1.	In the last month, how often have you been upset because of something that happened unexpectedly?	63 (21)	62 (20)	100 (33)	45 (15)	32 (11)	<.001*
2.	In the last month, how often have you felt that you were unable to control the important things in your life?	64 (21)	72 (23)	87 (29)	50 (17)	29 (10)	<.001*
3.	In the last month, how often have you felt nervous and “stressed”?	43 (14)	57 (19)	100 (33)	54 (18)	48 (16)	<.001*

4.	In the last month, how often have you felt confident about your ability to handle your personal problems?	28 (9)	50 (17)	102 (34)	73 (24)	49 (16)	< .001*
5.	In the last month, how often have you felt that things were going your way?	56 (18)	74 (24)	97 (32)	54 (18)	21 (7)	< .001*
6.	In the last month, how often have you found that you could not cope with all the things that you had to do?	52 (17)	84 (28)	106 (35)	42 (14)	18 (6)	< .001*
7.	In the last month, how often have you been able to control irritations in your life?	39 (13)	57 (19)	120 (40)	63 (21)	23 (7)	< .001*
8.	In the last month, how often have you felt that you were on top of things?	43 (14)	76 (25)	102 (34)	63 (21)	18 (6)	< .001*
9.	In the last month, how often have you been angered because of things that were outside of your control?	41 (14)	53 (17)	98 (32)	59 (19)	51 (17)	< .001*
10.	In the last month, how often have you felt difficulties piling up so high that you could not overcome them?	59 (19)	81 (27)	77 (25)	50 (17)	35 (12)	< .001*
	Average Response score for PSS-10	49 (16)	67 (22)	99 (33)	55 (18)	32 (10)	

*Chi square test; $p < 0.5$ is statistically significant; Abbreviations: - N=Never, AN=Almost Never, ST=Sometimes, FO=Fairly often, VO=Very often.

Response to PHQ-4 Questionnaire

Psychological distress was assessed using the Patient Health Questionnaire-4 (PHQ-4). A considerable proportion of participants reported symptoms of anxiety and depression, with 34% experiencing anxiety for several days and 25% reporting symptoms for more than half of the days. Similarly, 40% of participants reported reduced interest or pleasure in activities, and 29% experienced low mood for several days.

Overall, the findings indicate the presence of mild to moderate psychological distress among the study population. Detailed results are presented in **Table 4**

Table 4: Response towards the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-4; N-302).

No.	Variables	NAA N (%)	SD N (%)	MTHD N (%)	NED N (%)	P values
1.	How often have you been bothered by feeling nervous, anxious, or on the edge?	95 (31)	103 (34)	74 (25)	29 (10)	< .001*
2.	How often have you been bothered by not being able to stop or control worrying?	86 (28)	106 (35)	80 (26)	30 (10)	< .001*
3.	How often have you been bothered by little interest or pleasure in doing things?	64 (21)	119 (40)	91 (30)	28 (9)	< .001*
4.	How often have you been bothered by feeling down, depressed, or hopeless?	96 (32)	79 (26)	87 (29)	40 (13)	< .001*
	Average Response score for PHQ-4	85 (28)	101 (34)	83 (28)	31 (11)	

*Chi square test; $p < 0.5$ is statistically significant; Abbreviations: - NAA=Not At All, SD= Several Days, MTHD= More Than Half the Days, NED= Nearly Every Day.

Responses for AASIS Questionnaire

The impact of hair loss on participants was assessed using the Alopecia Areata Symptom Impact Scale (AASIS). The majority of participants reported mild to moderate levels of hair loss and associated symptoms, with 35% experiencing moderate scalp hair loss, while a large proportion reported no hair loss in body or eyelashes (65%). Regarding physical symptoms, most participants reported no tingling or numbness (58%) and no scalp irritation (47%). In terms of emotional impact, 24% reported no stress, while a smaller proportion (10%) reported experiencing stress frequently. Overall, the findings suggest that hair loss had a moderate impact on physical and emotional well-being among participants. Detailed results are presented in Table 5a&b.

Table- 5a: Response towards Alopecia Areata Symptoms Scale (AASIS).

No.	Variables	NN (%)	MN (%)	Mo N (%)	S N (%)	VSN (%)	P value
1.	Scalp hair loss	68 (23)	79 (26)	105 (35)	40 (13)	10 (3)	< .001*
2.	Body or eyelashes hair loss	195 (65)	68 (22)	29 (10)	8 (2)	2 (1)	< .001*
3.	Tingling/numbness of the scalp	176 (58)	68 (23)	42 (14)	10 (3)	6 (2)	< .001*
4.	Itchy, painful or irritated scalp	142 (47)	90 (30)	51 (17)	15 (5)	4 (1)	< .001*
5.	Feels stressed (anxious, worried or sad)	72 (24)	89 (29)	66 (22)	44 (15)	31 (10)	< .001*
	Average Response	130 (43)	79 (26)	57 (20)	23 (8)	11 (3)	

*Chi square test; $p < 0.5$ is statistically significant; N= No, M= Mild, Mo= Moderate, S= Severe, VS=Very Severe

Table-5b: Response towards Alopecia Areata Impact Scale (AASIS).

No.	Variables	NN (%)	RN (%)	ST N (%)	ON (%)	AN (%)	P value
6.	Overall physical well-being.	61 (20)	65 (21)	92 (31)	49 (16)	35 (12)	< .001*
7.	Overall emotional well-being.	40 (13)	89 (30)	88 (29)	49 (16)	36 (12)	< .001*
8.	Overall psychological well-being.	56 (18)	67 (22)	97 (32)	50 (17)	32 (11)	< .001*
9.	Overall social well-being	57 (19)	78 (26)	79 (26)	47 (16)	41 (13)	< .001*
10.	Overall quality of life.	51 (17)	50 (16)	87 (29)	61 (20)	53 (18)	.003
	Average Response	66	70	89	51	39	

	(17)	(19)	(29)	(17)	(13)	
*Chi square test; p<0.5 is statistically significant; Abbreviations: - N= Never, R= Rarely, ST= Some Times, O= Often, A= Always.						

Response towards modified hairdex questionnaire

The impact of hair loss on quality of life was assessed using the Modified Hairdex Questionnaire. The results indicated a significant psychological and social burden associated with hair loss. A considerable proportion of participants reported emotional distress, with 62% experiencing feelings of depression and 56% reporting embarrassment due to hair loss.

Physical symptoms were also noted, with 64% reporting itching or scratching of the scalp and 52% experiencing pain or discomfort. Social impact was evident, as 51% of participants reported avoiding social situations, and 44% expressed concerns about appearing older due to hair loss.

Despite these challenges, some participants maintained positive coping, with 29% reporting confidence and 31% expressing satisfaction with themselves despite hair loss. Overall, hair loss had a moderate to severe impact on quality of life among participants. Detailed results are presented in **Table 6**.

Table 6: Response towards Modified Hairdex Questionnaire.

No.	Variables	NN (%)	RN (%)	STN (%)	ON (%)	AN (%)	P value
1.	I have a sensation of pain or discomfort in my scalp.	144 (48)	94 (30)	44 (15)	14 (5)	6 (2)	<.001*
2.	There might be something seriously wrong with my hair.	101 (33)	90 (29)	77 (26)	23 (8)	11 (4)	<.001*
3.	My hair condition interferes with my work or activities.	116 (38)	87 (29)	58 (19)	33 (11)	8 (3)	<.001*
4.	My hair condition affects my social life.	129 (43)	76 (25)	58 (19)	26 (9)	13 (4)	<.001*
5.	The state of my hair is getting me down.	119 (39)	64 (21)	66 (22)	35 (12)	18 (6)	<.001*
6.	I have a sensation of itching and scratching my scalp.	109 (36)	83 (27)	63 (21)	35 (12)	12 (4)	<.001*
7.	I'm afraid my hair loss is going to get worse.	71 (23)	74 (25)	75 (25)	51 (17)	31 (10)	<.001*
8.	I often do things alone because of my hair loss.	149 (49)	74 (25)	50 (17)	16 (5)	13 (4)	<.001*
9.	When washing my hair, water affects the condition of my hair and scalp.	75 (25)	86 (29)	78 (25)	39 (13)	24 (8)	<.001*
10.	My scalp is in bad shape.	18 (6)	53 (18)	33 (11)	19 (6)	8 (3)	<.001*

11.	My scalp makes me oversensitive.	173 (57)	58 (19)	44 (15)	17 (6)	10 (3)	<.001*
12.	I feel embarrassed about my hair loss.	134 (44)	68 (23)	56 (19)	25 (8)	19 (6)	<.001*
13.	I feel depressed about my hair loss.	115 (38)	75 (25)	53 (17)	35 (12)	24 (8)	<.001*
14.	My scalp/hair condition makes me angry and irritable.	117 (38)	78 (26)	55 (18)	33 (11)	19 (7)	<.001*
15.	The state of my hair bothers me.	114 (37)	75 (25)	61 (20)	23 (8)	29 (10)	<.001*
16.	I worry that I look older than I am because of my hair.	171 (56)	65 (22)	33 (11)	22 (7)	11 (4)	<.001*
17.	I feel like an outsider because of my hair loss.	196 (65)	53 (18)	29 (10)	10 (3)	14 (4)	<.001*
18.	I hate my hair when I see it in the sink, in the comb, on the couch.	74 (25)	91 (29)	70 (23)	41 (14)	26 (9)	<.001*
19.	I look in the mirror every morning/night just to see if my hair is falling out.	103 (34)	91 (30)	58 (19)	30 (10)	20 (7)	<.001*
20.	My hair condition is under control.	69 (23)	81 (27)	74 (24)	54 (18)	24 (8)	<.001*
21.	Despite the hair loss, I am happy with myself.	49 (16)	58 (19)	65 (21)	39(13)	91 (31)	<.001*
22.	In general, despite the state of my hair loss, I have confidence.	50 (17)	55 (18)	58 (19)	51 (17)	88 (29)	<.001*
23.	Despite my hair/scalp condition, I still go to barber shop.	132 (44)	60 (20)	53 (18)	23 (7)	34 (11)	.002
24.	People talk behind my back about my hair loss.	174 (58)	46 (15)	49 (16)	19 (6)	14 (5)	<.001*
25.	I compare to others like bald head and feel lucky to have hair like this.	120 (40)	52 (17)	5 (19)	19 (6)	53 (18)	<.001*
	Average Responses	120 (40)	71 (24)	58 (23)	30 (10)	24 (8)	

*Chi square test; $p < 0.5$ is statistically significant; N=Never, R=Rarely, ST=Some times, O=Often, A=Always.

Association between Various study tools PSS-10, PHQ-4, AASIS, and the HD questionnaire and sociodemographic

The association between perceived stress levels and sociodemographic characteristics was analyzed using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10). A statistically significant association was observed between stress levels and variables such as age, duration of study, and family history of stress-related conditions ($p < 0.05$).

Participants aged 24–26 years showed higher levels of severe stress, while those aged 18–20 years predominantly exhibited moderate stress levels. Similarly, stress levels increased with the duration of study, with participants studying for longer periods reporting higher levels of

stress. Furthermore, participants with a family history of stress-related conditions demonstrated significantly higher stress levels compared to those without such history. These findings indicate that sociodemographic factors play an important role in influencing perceived stress among participants. Detailed results are presented in **Table 7**.

PHQ-4-assessed HL showed significant associations with age, duration of study, marital status, family history, and HL severity ($p < 0.05$). Participants aged 24–26 years exhibited the highest proportions of average and severe HL, while those aged above 26 years reported comparatively lower severity. Longer study duration was associated with increased HL severity, particularly among students studying for more than five years. Marital status also demonstrated a significant association, with singles and individuals in relationships reporting higher average and severe HL levels. Additionally, HL severity progressively increased across categories, indicating a significant rise in severity ($p = 0.023$). A significant association was also observed with family history ($p = 0.012$). However, gender, religion, diet, and native location showed no significant association with HL ($p > 0.05$).

The analysis using the AASIS Scale demonstrated significant associations between HL severity, study duration ($p = 0.009$), and HL progression ($p < 0.001$), while sociodemographic variables showed no significant association ($p > 0.05$). Participants with longer study duration reported higher proportions of average HL, suggesting that prolonged academic exposure may contribute to worsening HL severity. Increasing AASIS severity categories were associated with progressively severe HL levels, indicating a clear trend of HL progression among participants. These findings highlight the importance of early identification and management of HL among students.

Analysis using the Hairdex questionnaire revealed that age, duration of study, and HL severity were significantly associated with HL ($p < 0.05$). Participants aged 24–26 years showed the highest proportions of average and severe HL, whereas those aged above 26 years predominantly reported low HL. Increased study duration was also associated with greater HL severity, with severe HL rising among students studying for more than five years. Overall, 32% of participants had mild HL, 50% average HL, and 18% severe HL ($p < 0.001$). However, sociodemographic variables showed no significant association with HL severity ($p > 0.05$).

Variables (N=302)	N (%)	Stress Categories (PSS-10)				Stress Categories (PHQ-4)					AASIS				Hairdex			
		L N (%)	M N (%)	S N (%)	P Value	N N (%)	M N (%)	Mo N (%)	S N (%)	P Value	L N (%)	Mo N (%)	S N (%)	P Value	L N (%)	Mo N (%)	S N (%)	P Value
Age in years																		
18-20 years	186(62)	41 (22)	128 (69)	17 (9)	.047*	44(24)	58(31)	67(36)	17(9)	.000	74(40)	108(58)	4(2)	.714	103(55)	83(45)	0(0)	<.001*
21-23 years	75 (25)	14 (19)	49 (65)	12 (16)		17(23)	24(32)	21(28)	13(17)		32(43)	42(56)	1(1)		46(61)	23(31)	6(8)	
24-26 years	7 (2)	0 (0)	5 (71)	2 (28)		0(0)	1(14)	3(43)	3(43)		3(43)	4(57)	0(0)		2(29)	5(71)	0(0)	
>26 years	34 (11)	13 (38)	20 (59)	1 (3)		19(56)	7(21)	7(20)	1(3)		19(56)	14(41)	1(3)		27(79)	6(18)	1(3)	
Gender																		
Male	84 (28)	25 (30)	54 (64)	5 (6)	.074	28(33)	26(31)	23(28)	7(8)	.271	41(49)	41(49)	2(2)	.333	52(62)	31(37)	1(1)	.634
Female	218 (72)	43 (20)	148 (68)	27 (12)		52(24)	64(29)	75(35)	27(12)		87(40)	127(58)	4(2)		126(58)	86(39)	6(3)	
Religion																		
Hindu	250 (83)	60 (24)	167 (67)	23 (9)	.514	66(27)	81(32)	81(32)	23(9)	.084	106(42)	141(56)	4(2)	.327	147(59)	98(39)	6(2)	.791
Muslim	25 (8)	5 (20)	16 (64)	4 (16)		8(32)	2(8)	9(36)	6(24)		14(56)	10(40)	1(4)		17(68)	8(32)	0(0)	
Christian	26 (9)	3 (11)	18 (69)	5 (19)		6(23)	7(27)	8(31)	5(19)		8(31)	17(65)	1(4)		14(54)	11(42)	1(4)	
Marital Status																		
Single	265 (88)	55 (21)	178 (67)	31 (12)	.221	64(24)	79(30)	89(34)	33(12)	.039	108(41)	151(57)	6(2)	.294	154(58)	105(40)	6(2)	382
Married	26 (9)	9 (35)	16 (61)	1 (4)		14(54)	7(27)	5(19)	0(0)		16(62)	10(38)	0(0)		19(73)	6(23)	1(4)	
In relationship	11 (3)	4 (36)	7 (64)	0 (0)		2(19)	4(36)	4(36)	1(9)		4(36)	7(64)	0(0)		5(45)	6(55)	0(0)	

Diet																		
Veg	37 (12)	9 (25)	25 (69)	2 (6)	.074	11(30)	12(32)	9(24)	5(14)	.319	15(41)	21(57)	1(2)	.843	22(59)	15(41)	0(0)	.359
Non veg	42 (14)	10 (24)	30 (71)	2 (5)		17(40)	12(29)	10(24)	3(7)		21(50)	21(50)	0(0)		21(50)	21(50)	0(0)	
Mixed diet	222(74)	49 (22)	147 (66)	26(12)		51(23)	66(30)	79(35)	26(12)		92(42)	125(56)	5(2)		135(61)	80(36)	7(3)	
Eggetarian	1 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (100)		1(100)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)		0(0)	1(100)	0(0)		0(0)	1(100)	0(0)	
Duration																		
Below 1 Year	138 (46)	38 (27)	93 (67)	7 (5)	.024*	42(30)	41(30)	46(33)	9(7)	.013	72(52)	62(45)	4(3)	.009	94(68)	42(30)	2(2)	.024*
1-5 Years	129 (43)	24 (19)	87 (67)	18 (14)		23(18)	43(33)	43(33)	20(16)		41(32)	86(67)	2(1)		69(54)	57(44)	3(2)	
Above 5 Yrs	35 (11)	6 (17)	22 (63)	7 (20)		15(43)	6(17)	9(26)	5(14)		15(43)	20(57)	0(0)		15(43)	18(51)	2(6)	
Severity																		
Mild	98 (32)	29 (30)	64 (65)	5 (5)	.006	34(34)	29(30)	29(30)	6(6)	.023	51(52)	46(47)	1(1)	<.001*	68(69)	29(30)	1(1)	<.001*
Moderate	150 (50)	35 (24)	98 (65)	17 (11)		37(25)	50(33)	45(30)	18(12)		71(47)	75(50)	4(3)		92(61)	57(38)	1(1)	
Severe	54 (18)	4 (7)	40 (74)	10 (19)		9(17)	11(20)	24(44)	10(19)		6(11)	47(87)	1(2)		18(33)	31(58)	5(9)	
Family History																		
Yes	103 (34)	14 (13)	66 (64)	23 (22)	<.001*	23(22)	27(26)	33(32)	20(19)	.012	41(40)	60(58)	2(2)	.802	55(53)	44(43)	4(4)	.212
No	199 (66)	54 (27)	136 (68)	9 (5)		57(28)	63(32)	65(33)	14(7)		87(44)	108(54)	4(2)		123(62)	73(37)	3(1)	
Native Location																		
City	184 (61)	38 (21)	125 (68)	21 (11)	.074	51(28)	49(27)	62(33)	22(12)	.462	76(41)	105(57)	3(2)	.530	108(59)	72(29)	4(2)	.467
Town	64(21)	11(17)	44(69)	9(14)		15(23)	19(30)	21(33)	9(14)		24(38)	38(59)	2(3)		35(55)	26(41)	3(4)	
Rural	54(18)	19(35)	33(61)	2(4)		14(26)	22(41)	15(28)	3(5)		28(52)	25(46)	1(2)		35(65)	19(35)	0(0)	

Correlation matrix of each measured HL Associated Factors

Spearman's correlation analysis revealed significant positive correlations among psychological stress, anxiety, depression, and HL-related measures. PSS-10 showed moderate positive correlations with PHQ-4 ($r = 0.544$), PHQ-2 ($r = 0.553$), and GAD-2 ($r = 0.418$). Strong positive correlations were observed between PHQ-4 and PHQ-2 ($r = 0.877$), as well as between PHQ-4 and GAD-2 ($r = 0.876$). AASIS demonstrated weak positive correlations with PSS-10, PHQ-4, PHQ-2, and GAD-2 ($r = 0.292$ – 0.365). Similarly, Hairdex (HD) showed weak to moderate positive correlations with all measured variables, including PSS-10, PHQ-4, PHQ-2, GAD-2, and AASIS ($r = 0.293$ – 0.402). These findings suggest a potential association between psychological stress, anxiety, depression, and HL severity.

VARIABLES	M(IQR)	PSS	PHQ4	PHQ2	GAD2	AASIS
PSS	19 (9)					
PHQ4	5 (5)	.544**				
PHQ2	2 (3)	.553**	.877**			
GAD2	3 (3)	.418**	.876**	.549**		
AASIS	15 (9)	.292**	.365**	.330**	.313**	
HD	29 (23)	.293**	.402**	.373**	.346**	.355**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Correlation Coefficient:
 0.90 to 1.00: Very high positive correlation; 0.70 to 0.90: High positive correlation;
 0.50 to 0.70: Moderate positive correlation; 0.30 to 0.50: Low positive correlation

The Overall Total Score for Associated factors of HL. The results obtained from multiple assessment scales provided a comprehensive evaluation of their influence on HL. Statistical analyses, including mean (SD), median (IQR), and Chi-square tests, were performed to determine significance. The PSS-10 scale indicated considerable perceived stress among participants, with a mean score of 18.53 ± 6.86 , median of 19 (IQR = 9), and scores ranging from 0–40; the findings were statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 209.61$, $p < 0.001$). The PHQ-4 scale, used to assess psychological distress, showed a mean score of 4.82 ± 2.95 , median of 5 (IQR = 5), and a range of 0–12, with significant results ($\chi^2 = 84.04$, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, the PHQ-2 scale assessing depressive symptoms demonstrated a mean score of 2.31 ± 1.71 , median of 2 (IQR = 3), and scores ranging from 0–6, which was also statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 99.32$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 9: The Overall Total Score for factors associated with Hair loss of the Study participants.

Variable	Items	Mean (SD)	Median (IQR)	Range	X ²	P Value
PSS-10	10	18.53 ± 6.86	19 (9)	0 → 40	209.61	<0.001
PHQ-4	4	4.82 ± 2.95	5 (5)	0 → 12	84.04	<0.001
PHQ-2	2	2.31 ± 1.71	2 (3)	0 → 6	99.32	<0.001
GAD-2	2	2.50 ± 1.63	3 (3)	0 → 6	52.82	<0.001
AASIS	10	14.35 ± 6.20	15 (9)	0 → 35	171.00	<0.001
HD	25	30.79 ± 25.73	29(23)	0 → 85	124.15	<0.001

DISCUSSION

Principal Findings

This cross-sectional study was conducted among pharmacy students and faculty members at a private institution to evaluate the prevalence of hair loss (HL), associated risk factors, psychological impact, and awareness regarding preventive and treatment measures. Previous studies have reported significant associations between HL and psychological as well as hereditary factors. Paul et al. examined 387 male participants in the National Capital Region of India and identified stress, depression, itchy scalp, and family history as major contributors to HL severity. Similarly, Abdulaziz S.A et al. assessed 1,080 individuals in Al Majma'ah, Saudi Arabia, and reported a higher prevalence of HL among females, with stress strongly associated with the condition. In comparison with these earlier studies, the present study achieved a comparatively higher response rate and included both students and faculty members, thereby providing broader institutional representation.

The study utilized both adopted and adapted questionnaires to comprehensively assess stress, psychological distress, awareness, and contributing factors associated with HL. Standardized tools included the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) and the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-4), along with a modified stress factor questionnaire specifically tailored to meet the objectives of the study. The questionnaire comprised four distinct scales designed to evaluate various determinants related to HL. Reliability testing demonstrated excellent internal consistency across all instruments. The Cronbach's alpha values for PSS-10, PHQ-4, AASIS, and the HD questionnaire were each reported as $\alpha = 0.99$, indicating outstanding reliability. Furthermore, the adapted HL questionnaire underwent content, construct, and face validity assessment, and a strong positive correlation was observed among all measured attributes.

A total of 302 participants were included in the study. The majority belonged to the 18–20 years age group (62%), were female (72%), and identified as Hindu (83%). Regarding

educational background, 52% were Bachelor of Pharmacy (BPharm) students and 38% were Doctor of Pharmacy (Pharm D) graduates. Most participants were unmarried (88%) and resided in urban areas (61%). Average levels of HL were reported by 50% of participants, while severe HL was observed in 18%. Stress-related HL was particularly prominent among fifth-year (67%) and sixth-year students (74%). Among participants with a family history of HL, 64% reported average stress levels. Familial occurrence of HL was most commonly observed in fathers (43.04%), followed by mothers (24.68%). In terms of hair care practices, 40.19% of participants used hard water for hair washing, while 61.96% relied primarily on shampoo-based cleansing methods. The majority (86.13%) practiced home-based hair care, whereas only 2.32% sought consultation from dermatologists.

The first assessment tool explored participants' awareness regarding HL causes, preventive measures, and treatment responses. Stress (63%), iron deficiency (66%), and testosterone imbalance (33%) were identified as common perceived causes of HL. Among medication-related causes, anti-cancer drugs were most frequently recognized, with 75% awareness among participants. Commonly adopted preventive approaches included increased protein intake (62%) and the use of minoxidil or biotin-based serums (61%). Overall, the findings suggest a moderate level of awareness regarding HL causes and preventive strategies, particularly concerning the role of stress and nutrition. However, uncertainty remained regarding the effectiveness of available treatments and hair transplantation procedures, and a considerable proportion of participants had not attempted any form of treatment despite acknowledging preventive measures.

The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) was employed to assess the extent and influence of stress on HL among participants. Approximately 68% of participants reported experiencing HL at varying levels, which closely corresponds with findings from the Saudi Arabian study reporting a prevalence of 71.3%. Additionally, a strong association was identified between psychological distress and HL, as measured using the PHQ-4 questionnaire. The PHQ-4 tool evaluated symptoms of anxiety and depression experienced during the previous two weeks. The findings revealed that 10% of participants experienced anxiety nearly every day, while another 10% reported daily uncontrollable worry. Approximately 9% of participants reported a persistent loss of interest in activities, and 13% experienced feelings of depression or hopelessness nearly every day. These findings indicate a substantial burden of anxiety and

depressive symptoms among the study population and demonstrate a statistically significant relationship between psychological distress and HL ($p < 0.001$).

The Alopecia Areata Impact Scale (AASIS) assessed the physical and emotional impact of hair loss (HL) among participants. Approximately 23% reported no scalp HL, while 35% experienced average HL. Most participants (65%) reported no body or eyelash hair loss. Emotional well-being was moderately affected, with 24% reporting no stress and 13% experiencing emotional distress. Findings from the Hairdex Questionnaire showed that HL negatively affected emotional and social well-being, leading to embarrassment, discomfort, anger, and depressive feelings among many participants. Despite these challenges, some participants maintained confidence and continued regular social activities. Overall, the findings highlight the significant psychological burden associated with HL and emphasize the need for holistic management addressing both dermatological and emotional health.

The study identified significant associations between perceived stress and demographic variables such as age, duration of study, and family background. Participants aged 24–26 years and those with a family history of stress-related conditions reported higher stress and HL severity. Significant associations were observed between study duration ($p = 0.009$) and HL severity ($p < 0.001$). Participants with longer study duration commonly experienced average HL, while severe HL was more prevalent among older participants. However, variables such as gender, religion, diet, marital status, and native location showed no significant association with HL ($p > 0.05$). Overall, 32% of participants reported mild HL, 50% average HL, and 18% severe HL.

Limitations

The study included a diverse participant population; however, the predominance of female participants may have introduced selection bias. The cross-sectional study design limited the ability to establish a causal relationship between stress and hair loss (HL). Use of self-reported questionnaires may also have resulted in reporting bias. Additionally, the findings may not be generalizable to other institutions due to variations in academic stress and institutional policies. The study did not assess long-term HL patterns or participant histories such as substance use and mental health conditions. External factors including lifestyle, pollution, and dietary habits were also not evaluated.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that psychological stress is a major contributing factor to perceived HL among students and faculty members in private pharmacy colleges. Significant associations between HL and psychological measures such as PSS, PHQ-4, and GAD-2 indicate that stress and emotional well-being play an important role in HL. Although genetic and environmental factors also contribute, improving mental health and implementing stress management programs within educational institutions may help reduce stress-related HL. Further studies are recommended to explore targeted interventions for stress reduction and hair health improvement.

Future Recommendations

The findings suggest that academic-related factors significantly contribute to stress among students. Educational institutions should consider implementing strategies and mental health support programs to reduce academic stress and improve overall student well-being. Further large-scale and longitudinal studies are needed to better understand the relationship between stress and HL.

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